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Supporting Information for

Tracing a Mantle Component of Paleo-fluids in the Red River Fault

Wenqing Huang¹, Pei Ni^{2,*}, Jungui Zhou¹, Ting Shui³, Xiaoyong Cao¹, Junyi Pan², Fanwei Meng⁴, Hui Dai⁵, Wei Cai¹, and Mingsen Fan²

¹National Center of Inspection and Testing on Quality of Gold and Silver Products, Nanjing Institute of Product Quality Inspection, Nanjing, China.

²State Key Laboratory for Mineral Deposits Research, Institute of Geo-Fluids, Frontiers Science Center for Critical Earth Material Cycling, School of Earth Sciences and Engineering, Nanjing University, Nanjing, China.

³Nanjing Center, China Geological Survey, Nanjing, China.

⁴School of Resources and Geosciences, China University of Mining and Technology, Xuzhou, China.

⁵Anhui Provincial Institute of Geological Experiments, Hefei, China.

Corresponding author: Pei Ni (peini@nju.edu.cn)

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Introduction

The supporting information provides a detailed description of laboratory measurements (Text S1) and some supporting figures (Figures S1–S6) and tables (Table S1–S3).

Text S1.

Field work was conducted in 2023 and a total of 12 marble samples were collected from freshly exposed road-cuts and quarries. The samples were then characterized using the TESCAN Integrated Mineral Analyzer to analyze the potential paragenetic relationship between ruby, pyrite, and spinel. Petrographic observation was carried out on ruby and spinel to observe the fluid inclusions, which were identified based on the capture sequence relative to the host minerals. Carbon and oxygen isotopes of carbonate minerals of the marbles were determined to detect the potential mantle carbon isotopic characteristics.

Mineral maps and backscattered electron (BSE) images were acquired using a TESCAN Integrated Mineral Analyzer at Nanjing Hongchuang Exploration Technology Service Co., Ltd., to determine the paragenetic relationship. This instrument is a fully automated system, equipped with an ultrafast scintillation detector for high-quality BSE imaging and four silicon-drifted energy dispersive X-ray detectors. The operation conditions were set at 25 kV and 8.65 nA.

Noble gas isotopes were analyzed using a sector-type noble gas mass spectrometer (Noblesse, Nu Instruments Ltd.) at the Institute of Geology and Geophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences. The mass resolution of the Noblesse spectrometer is high enough to differentiate the peaks of ^3He and HD^+ (Guo et al., 2022). Before analyses, about 0.1–0.4 g of the mineral separates was sequentially cleaned in an ultrasonic bath with distilled water, ethanol, and high-purity acetone, with each wash over 10 minutes. The samples were then dried in an oven at $\sim 75^\circ\text{C}$ and loaded in a hydraulic-driven crusher. The samples were baked in a high vacuum system at 120°C for 48 hours. To minimize the effects of isotopes produced in situ and gases adsorbed by the atmosphere, the gas in the sample was extracted by vacuum crushing at a pressure of about 2000 psi. All samples were crushed at room temperature, and the released gases were purified by a cold trap at liquid nitrogen temperature and four groups of SAES Zr-Al getters (two working at room temperature and two at 450°C). Helium and neon are then separated by a 35K cryogenic cold pump. Helium and neon were respectively fed into the Noblesse noble gas mass spectrometer for measurement. In the process of mass spectrometry measurement, a GP50 zirconium aluminum pump and liquid nitrogen cold trap were used to minimize the partial pressure of the residual gas. Procedural blank was monitored before each sample run and was negligible in all cases when compared to the sample signals. Helium isotopic ratios were normalized against an artificial helium standard (He Standard of Japan; HESJ) with a recommended $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ value of $20.415 \pm 0.029 R_A$ (Mishima et al., 2018). Analytical results are presented in Table S2.

Figure S1. Simplified geologic map showing the Yuanjiang marble-hosted ruby deposit is located in the Ailao Shan range of the Red River fault zone. Modified after Leloup et al. (1995).

Figure S2. The marble samples examined in this study were collected from freshly exposed road cuts (a) and quarry (b).

Figure S3. Representative ruby- and spinel-bearing marble samples from Yuanjiang, shown in (a) and (b), respectively.

Figure S4. Typical fluid inclusion trails in healed fractures that do not transect the host grains of spinel (a) and ruby (b), suggesting a pseudo-secondary origin.

Figure S5. BSE images (a–c) and mineral mapping (d) show the paragenetic relationships between ruby and pyrite (a–c), as well as between ruby and spinel (d). Pyrite and ruby exhibit relationships of mutual inclusion (a–b) and direct contact (c), strongly suggesting

that they crystallized simultaneously. The direct contact between ruby and spinel also suggest that they form a paragenetic assemblage.

Figure S6. The tectonic sketch of the India-Eurasia collision depicts the distribution and the mineralization ages of marble-hosted ruby deposits in Central and Southeastern Asia. Modified from Garnier et al. (2008). Notably, the occurrences of ruby are spatially closely associated with major structural features (see also Table S3).

Sample no.	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)	$^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ (R/R _A)	$^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$	Related fault	Data source
Panamik	34.78	77.54	0.101	not given	KF	Klemperer et al., 2013
Changlung	34.94	77.47	0.725	not given	KF	Klemperer et al., 2013
Mengshi	31.13	80.75	2.225	not given	KF	Klemperer et al., 2013
Thirthapuri	31.19	80.93	0.38	3.8	KF	Hoke et al., 2000
Thirthapuri	31.19	80.93	0.30	17.4	KF	Hoke et al., 2000
190503-YJ	23.52	101.90	0.045	57.1	RRF	Zhang et al., 2022
43	25.34	100.51	0.38	28.6	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
44	25.31	100.48	0.07	14.8	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
45	25.17	100.32	0.24	97	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
46	24.68	100.61	0.11	46.8	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
47	23.52	101.90	0.04	62.2	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
48	23.36	102.94	0.17	56.1	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
49	23.33	102.49	0.62	46.2	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
50	23.17	102.70	0.28	33	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
51	22.99	103.36	0.40	42.5	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
52	22.94	103.86	0.14	266.8	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
53	22.93	103.43	0.45	41.6	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
54	22.91	103.49	0.46	26.3	RRF	Zhou et al., 2020
13	22.91	103.49	0.47	6.1	RRF	Wang et al., 2020
14	22.93	103.43	0.46	37.5	RRF	Wang et al., 2020
15	22.90	103.46	0.43	24.0	RRF	Wang et al., 2020
16	22.99	103.36	0.39	38.4	RRF	Wang et al., 2020
17	23.00	103.11	0.09	53.2	RRF	Wang et al., 2020

Table S1. Compiled geochemical data of hot springs within the Karakoram fault (KF) and Red River fault (RRF).

Sample no.	Host mineral	$^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ (R/R_A , 1σ) ^a	Mantle He (%) ^b	$^4\text{He}/^{20}\text{Ne}$	^4He (cm^3 STP g^{-1} H_2O)
YSK-1-1	Ruby	0.77 ± 0.10	9.35	1149	1.06×10^{-7}
YSK-2-1	Ruby	0.24 ± 0.06	2.70	25548	1.41×10^{-7}
YSK-3-1	Ruby	0.19 ± 0.02	2.10	12517	3.17×10^{-7}
YSK-3-2	Ruby	0.40 ± 0.07	4.79	–	1.37×10^{-7}
YSK-4-1	Ruby	0.14 ± 0.01	1.51	42409	1.23×10^{-6}
YSK-4-2	Ruby	0.13 ± 0.01	1.36	14279	1.21×10^{-6}
YSK-5-1	Ruby	0.24 ± 0.03	2.80	3187	1.70×10^{-7}
LYSR066-1	Spinel	0.24 ± 0.03	2.78	1819	0.71×10^{-7}
LYSR066-2	Spinel	0.18 ± 0.03	1.98	4916	1.28×10^{-7}
LYSR068-1	Spinel	0.09 ± 0.03	0.90	–	0.78×10^{-7}
LYSR068-2	Spinel	0.44 ± 0.08	5.30	2835	0.39×10^{-7}
LYSR068-	Pyrite	0.50 ± 0.07	6.04	1101	1.57×10^{-7}
Crust	–	0.02	–	>1000	–
Mantle	–	8.00	–	>1000	–

Note: ^aHelium isotopic ratio (R) is normalized to the atmospheric ratio (R_A) with a value of 1.39×10^{-6} . ^bMantle helium proportions are calculated assuming a binary mixing between the mantle and crust based on the measured $^3\text{He}/^4\text{He}$ ratios.

Table S2. Helium isotopic results and helium/neon abundance ratios of fluid inclusions within ruby, spinel, and pyrite from the Red River fault.

Deposit	Country	Structure feature	Distance between deposit and structure feature (km)	Reference
Nangimali	Pakistan	Main Mantle Thrust	35	Pêcher et al., 2002
Hunza	Pakistan	Main Karakoram Thrust	25	Garnier et al., 2006
Jegdalek	Afghanistan	Indus Suture Zone	0 ^a	Garnier et al., 2008
Snezhnoe	Tajikistan	Rushan-Pshart deep fault	15	Sorokina et al., 2015
Chumar	Nepal	Main Central Thrust	5	Smith et al., 1997
Ruyil	Nepal	Main Central Thrust	5	Smith et al., 1997
Mogok	Myanmar	Sagaing deep fault	30	Guo et al., 2021
Luc Yen	Vietnam	Red River fault	0–<10 ^b	Van Long et al., 2013
Yen Bai	Vietnam	Red River fault	3–10	Khoi et al., 2011
Yuanjiang	China	Red River fault	0	Luo & Yu, 1999

Note: ^avalue 0 represent the ruby deposit is just within the fault. ^bRanges used when multiple ruby occurrences were documented.

Table S3. Compilation of the distance between Asian marble-hosted ruby deposits and their respective nearby major structure feature.